

1 **Comments on the paper entitled “Particle size distribution: An experimental study using southern**
2 **African reduction methods and raw materials” by de la Peña et al. (2022).**

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7 Abstract: The data published by de la Peña et al. (2022) on the particle size composition of South
8 African experimental lithic assemblages complement the corpus of data already available and
9 extends the referential that can be used for the taphonomic study of archaeological assemblages.
10 From this perspective, the purpose of particle size analysis is to determine whether the collected
11 lithic assemblage has been sorted by sedimentary processes and, therefore, whether its integrity has
12 been preserved, which may have important implications for the relevance of the economic study.
13 Contrary to de la Peña et al. (2022) who used the entire size distribution of products larger than 2
14 mm in their study, we argue that only the fraction greater than 5 mm should be considered in
15 archaeological studies, because the collection of knapping debris is easier and more comprehensive,
16 the variability of the experimental assemblages is lower, and this fraction is sufficient to test the
17 preservation of the integrity of archaeological assemblages. The new data also raises the question of
18 the influence of the type of raw material source used (primary or alluvial) and the size of the blocks
19 on the particle size composition of the debitage products.

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21 **Introduction**

22 In a recent paper, de la Peña et al.¹ studied in detail the particle size distribution of the knapping
23 products of blocks of various raw materials present in the close environment of South African
24 Palaeolithic sites and according to debitage modalities specific to the archaeological record. The
25 results obtained are interesting and usefully complement those already obtained with raw materials
26 and debitage modalities from other regions of the world, in particular from Europe² and East Africa³.
27 They highlight a greater variability in size distribution than that obtained for the European dataset,
28 both dependent on raw material type and knapping methods. In particular, some rocks, such as
29 chalcedony, jasper, and quartz, release a greater amount of small debris (sieve mesh $d = 2$ to 5 mm,
30 equivalent to a real piece width $w = 2.8$ to 7.1 mm, see²) than hornfels, rhyolite, quartzite, and flint.
31 Bipolar debitage on anvil and shaping also produce more small debris than *Levallois* and discoidal
32 debitage. Therefore, the authors conclude that this strong variability significantly weakens the
33 possibility of using the particle size analysis of lithic material to determine, in the framework of an
34 archaeological taphonomy analysis⁴, whether the Palaeolithic assemblages were affected by post-
35 depositional hydraulic sorting (overland flow, stream flow...).

36 In their study, de la Peña et al.¹ use the entire particle size distribution of products larger than $d = 2$
37 mm similar to what had been proposed for the European dataset^{5,2}. This size range was initially
38 chosen⁵ because it was considered the most appropriate to highlight hydraulic sorting of lithic
39 assemblages, insofar as small-sized debris are the most prone to being transported by flows. In
40 practice, however, the inclusion of debris smaller than $d = 5$ mm has proven to be of poor interest for
41 application to the study of Palaeolithic sites. The main reasons are: (1) the collection of these small

42 debris is constraining and requires time-consuming sieving in the field; identification of knapping
 43 debris from the sieve refusals is often difficult when they are mixed with a large quantity of natural
 44 detrital particles, and exhaustive collection is rarely assured; (2) the interest of the fraction smaller
 45 than $d = 5$ mm in the techno-economic study of a lithic assemblage is limited, since this fraction
 46 essentially corresponds to waste that was not the object of particular attention (e.g., export or
 47 import to the site) by the Palaeolithic knappers. Therefore, this fraction is usually neither used to
 48 assess debitage techniques nor considered in the economic study.

49 From the perspective of a taphonomic study, the purpose of particle size analysis is to determine
 50 whether the collected lithic assemblage has been sorted and, therefore, whether its integrity has
 51 been preserved. A loss of integrity has important implications for the relevance of the economic
 52 study. Hydraulic sorting usually leads to an under-representation of certain artifact size categories
 53 (usually small to medium elements). The archaeological interpretation must consider this and the
 54 deficit cannot be attributed to human behavior (segmentation of the *chaîne opératoire* in different
 55 places, export of some elements, lack of re-sharpening of tools at the site...). To achieve the
 56 objectives of the taphonomic analysis and answer the questions posed⁴, it appears more efficient to
 57 consider only the fraction greater than 5 mm in the particle size analysis. This fraction proved to be
 58 sufficiently informative to highlight hydraulic sorting. The assemblages for which such a sorting was
 59 identified have a limited interest to document a specific management of the lithic material by the
 60 Palaeolithic groups because their integrity has not been preserved. For example, many Lower and
 61 Middle Paleolithic assemblages from southwestern France have shown significant depletion of small
 62 ($5 \text{ mm} \leq d < 10 \text{ mm}$) and medium ($10 \text{ mm} \leq d < 20 \text{ mm}$) size elements due to overland flow^{2,6}, which
 63 has often resulted in an over-representation of macro-tools (bifaces, cleavers, large flakes) and cores
 64 in the collected material.

65 **Material and methods**

66 In this study, we used the particle size distribution of experimental debitage from the work of De la
 67 Peña et al.¹ for South Africa, Bertran et al.² for Europe and Maurin et al.³ for East Africa. As
 68 mentioned above, these debitage were produced using a variety of methods similar to those
 69 deduced from regional Early, Middle and Upper Palaeolithic archaeological assemblages, and include
 70 (1) debitage on avil ("axial bipolar debitage"), (2) discoidal debitage ("freehand multifacial
 71 discoidal"), (3) *Levallois* debitage ("freehand recurrent centripetal"), (4) laminar debitage ("freehand
 72 unipolar/bipolar") and (5) bifacial shaping. The raw materials used are equally varied, and include
 73 blocks from primary outcrops for the South African data (chalcedony, jasper, quartz, quartzite,
 74 hornfels, and rhyolite), flint blocks and alluvial pebbles of quartzite for the European data, and
 75 alluvial pebbles of vein quartz and Precambrian leucocratic gneiss (collectively referred to as "quartz"
 76 in ³). In all these studies, the pieces were hand-sieved, and the sieve meshes retained here are 5, 10
 77 and 20 mm.

78 We recalculated the South African data excluding the fraction smaller than 5 mm (Supplementary
 79 Information 1) from the S1 file of De la Peña et al.¹. For the European dataset, the values were taken
 80 from Table 4 in Bertran et al.². The East African data were compiled from the original file of piece
 81 counts made by T. Maurin (not available in Maurin et al.³). Only the experimental debitage for which
 82 the number of pieces ≥ 5 mm greater than or equal to 39 were considered for the European and East
 83 African datasets. All the results were then plotted on a triangular diagram with the following poles:

84 fine fraction ($5 \text{ mm} \leq d < 10 \text{ mm}$), medium fraction ($10 \text{ mm} \leq d < 20 \text{ mm}$) and coarse fraction (≥ 20
85 mm).

86 **Results and discussion**

87 The new datasets are compared in Figure 1. The main conclusions that can be drawn are the
88 following:

89 (1) The variability of the particle size distribution for the South African data is lower when the fine
90 fraction is not considered. The area of distributions largely overlaps that of the European data.

91 (2) Many South African distributions are characterized by a lower proportion of coarse elements than
92 in the European data. This low proportion appears to be associated primarily with certain raw
93 material types, particularly chalcedony, jasper, and quartz, as previously shown by de la Peña et al.¹.
94 On the other hand, the distribution range for hornfels, rhyolite, and quartzite, is close to that of the
95 European data for quartzite and flint. For the South African dataset, bipolar debitage also produces
96 significantly fewer coarse elements than other modalities. However, this effect is not apparent in the
97 European dataset, where the distribution of bipolar knapping products (“anvil”, fig. 1) does not
98 diverge from that of other debitage methods.

99 (3) No European and South African distribution plot in the right part of the diagram (dominant
100 medium and/or coarse elements), which corresponds to the composition of assemblages affected by
101 a depletion in fine elements caused by hydraulic sorting. Therefore, the potential of the particle size
102 analysis of lithic material for taphonomic analysis does not appear to be really impacted by the
103 inclusion of South African data. However, the scarcity of coarse elements ($d \geq 20 \text{ mm}$) in some
104 assemblages suggests that the artifact size classes have to be adapted in South African studies for
105 more appropriate visualization of size distributions. An earlier study of Oldowan lithic assemblages
106 from the Omo Valley in East Africa³ also faced a similar problem, as elements $\geq 20 \text{ mm}$ wide
107 accounted for less than 10% of the total. In this study, the authors adopted the following classes: 5-
108 10 mm, 10-15 mm and $\geq 15 \text{ mm}$, which allowed revealing the influence of hydraulic sorting on some
109 archaeological assemblages.

110 The main information that emerges from the South African data is the presence of particle size
111 distributions characterized by a lower proportion of coarse elements than for the European data. The
112 raw material type seems to be the main factor driving this variability. The raw materials used for the
113 European experiments consist of flint blocks, which are generally very homogeneous, and alluvial
114 quartzite pebbles, which are resistant and show only rare fissures. In contrast, the South African raw
115 materials releasing abundant small elements are fragile rocks (jasper) and micro-fissured (diaclasses,
116 joints between crystals) rocks (chalcedony, xenomorphic quartz) coming from primary sources (rock
117 outcrops as indicated by ¹). The blocks have not undergone alluvial transport, which removes the
118 most fragile, highly fissured parts. It is likely that, for these rocks, a large part of the coarse elements
119 broke up during knapping because of internal micro-fissures. This raw material effect likely explains
120 why the distributions obtained from alluvial quartzite pebbles for bipolar debitage in the European
121 dataset do not exhibit a higher proportion of small elements than the other modalities, unlike the
122 South African data.

123 Knapping experiments carried out using alluvial pebbles of vein quartz and Precambrian leucocratic
124 gneiss using debitage modalities specific to the Oldowan industries of the Shungura Formation (Omo

125 Valley, Ethiopia), i.e., bipolar and direct freehand debitage, also highlight another factor in the size
126 composition of the knapping products. Because of the small dimension of the alluvial pebbles
127 available in the vicinity of the sites, the size of the products of both the experimental and
128 archaeological debitage does not exceed 45 mm in maximum width and small elements largely
129 predominate (fig. 1). This impact of the size of the (available or chosen) raw material blocks remains
130 poorly documented in the literature. In the various knapping experiments, the knappers chose blocks
131 whose dimensions seemed suitable to obtain blanks comparable to those of the archaeological
132 record. These dimensions are generally not specified. The size of the blanks desired (variable
133 according to the Palaeolithic techno-complexes, ranging from very large flakes transformed into
134 cleavers in the Acheulean to the typical bladelets of the Upper Palaeolithic) has an influence on the
135 particle size composition, mainly on the proportion of large elements. Together with other factors of
136 variability, this phenomenon should be considered in the interpretation of the particle size analysis of
137 archaeological assemblages and deserves further investigation.

138 **Conclusion**

139 In conclusion, the new data¹ on the particle size composition of South African experimental lithic
140 assemblages complement the corpus of data already available and extends the referential that can
141 be used for the taphonomic analysis of archaeological assemblages. However, we argue that only the
142 fraction greater than 5 mm should be considered in the studies, both because the collection of
143 knapping debris in archaeological contexts is easier and more comprehensive, the variability of the
144 experimental assemblages is lower, and this fraction is sufficient to test the preservation of the
145 integrity of archaeological assemblages. The data also have the merit of pointing out the influence of
146 raw material types, probably largely related to the type of block sources (primary or alluvial).

147 **Acknowledgement**

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149 and for his constructive comments on the manuscript.

150 **Data Availability Statement**

151 All relevant data are within the paper and its Supporting Information file.

152 **Competing interests**

153 The author declares that there is no conflict of interest.

154 **References**

- 155 1. De la Peña P, Thomas M, Molefyane TR. Particle size distribution: An experimental study using
156 southern African reduction methods and raw materials. PLoS ONE. 2022; 17(12): e0278867.
157 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0278867>
- 158 2. Bertran P, Lenoble A, Todisco D, Desroziers PM, Sorensen M. Particle size distribution of lithic
159 assemblages and taphonomy of Palaeolithic sites. Journal of Archaeological Science. 2012; 39, 3148-
160 3166.
- 161 3. Maurin T, Bertran P, Delagnes A, Boisserie JR. Early hominin landscape use in the Lower Omo
162 Valley, Ethiopia: Insights from the taphonomical analysis of Oldowan occurrences in the Shungura
163 Formation (Member F). Journal of Human Evolution. 2017; 11: 33-53.

164 4. Bertran P, Todisco D, Bordes JG, Discamps E, Vallin L. Perturbation assessment in archaeological
165 sites as part of the taphonomic study: A review of methods used to document the impact of natural
166 processes of site formation and archaeological interpretations. *PALEO*. 2019; 30(1): 52-75.

167 5. Lenoble A. Ruissellement et formation des sites préhistoriques: référentiel actualiste et exemples
168 d'application au fossile. *British Archaeological Report*; 2005.

169 6. Connet N, Bertran P, Claud E, Larmignat B, Boitard E. Dynamique d'occupation au Paléolithique
170 moyen, apport de l'analyse croisée géo-archéologique et techno-économique du site « Les pièces de
171 Monsieur Jarnac » à Bourg-Charente (Charente). *Bulletin de la Société préhistorique française*. 2022;
172 119(2): 179-221.

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174 **Figure caption**

175 Figure 1: Particle size composition of experimental lithic assemblages. A, B - European dataset, after²;
176 C, D - South African dataset, after¹; E - Omo Valley dataset, East Africa, modified after³. d: sieve
177 mesh; w: hand-measured artefact width.

178 Supplementary information

179 SI 1: Table of size composition of experimental knapping products for the fraction ≥ 5 mm. European
180 dataset is from ²; Omo-type (Shungura Formation, East Africa) Oldowan dataset recalculated from ³;
181 South African dataset recalculated from ¹.

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